
Managing Classroom Conflicts: Effective Resolution Strategies in English Classrooms

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ABSTRACT: The purpose of the study was to examine the critical role of conflict resolution in the English classroom where diverse ethnic and linguistic backgrounds often contributed to misunderstandings, power struggles, and behavioral differences. This research focuses on common classroom conflicts, the drivers of conflicts, and the methods provided for effective resolution that are used in public schools. The research was conducted among six secondary public school English teachers who were interviewed, with all providing their perspectives and approaches to conflict resolution. Researchers use semi-structured interview methods with teachers. Data were analyzed following Creswell's qualitative design and inductive coding techniques. The research revealed the primary challenge of English classroom environments: conflicts are often the result of language difficulties, cultural issues, and interpersonal relationship problems, all of which weaken from student participation and upset the overall classroom environment. Teachers resolve these conflicts mainly through collaborative learning experiences using mediation, encouraging empathy, and using systematic classroom management strategies. The research emphasizes the need to empower and develop educators with high-level conflict resolution skills that are needed in promoting peaceful and inclusive learning communities towards the aspirations of sustainable development.

KEYWORDS: conflict resolution, classroom management, teacher training, cultural diversity, qualitative research

I. INTRODUCTION

It is challenging to avoid conflicts due to differing perspectives in discussions, and in education, how participants achieve equilibrium is likely to affect the degree of learning, student engagement, and even relationships between students and teachers (Deutsch, 1973; Johnson and Johnson, 2009). As a space with many languages and cultures (Kramsch, 1998; Canagarajah, 2013), the English classroom can sometimes harbor students with misconceptions, unrealistic expectations, and competing objectives of themselves. In the absence of addressing these issues, the learning experience may be compromised, leading to an unproductive learning environment that negatively impacts on the academic and social development of the learners (Hattie, 2009; Slavin, 2018). However, when addressed constructively, conflicts can transform into opportunities for development through improved communication abilities, understanding, and constructive relationships (Vygotsky, 1978; Coser, 1956). The aim of this study is to clarify the nature of conflicts in English classrooms, their causes, and the strategies employed by educators to resolve them so that the positive outcomes of such conflicts can enhance overall school life (Bickmore, 2011; Johnson and Johnson, 2020).

Issues in the classroom can range from personal conflicts occurring within the pupils to conflicts existing between the pupils and the teachers. Johnson (2018) notes that in the English classroom, especially those who are multilingual, conflicts result from language and cultural differences. For example, some frustrations arise as misunderstandings from a struggle to articulate one's thoughts, which is common among non-native speakers of English. On the other hand, Smith and Lee (2020) show that when students hail from different cultures, their expectation of how participants are to behave in the class may not only differ but can also cause environments which stress the students. All these conflicts tend to interfere with the learning exercise and the psychological wellbeing of the teachers, and the students is adversely affected.

Resolving conflicts quickly is very important in promoting a good and functioning classroom environment. Deutsch (1973) indicates that conflicts can be constructive if managed properly, because they can serve as opportunities for dialogue, problem solving, and even building relationships. In the case of English classrooms which are often multicultural, the strategies of conflict resolution have to take into consideration the complexities of cultural and linguistic diversity. Further, teachers who adjust their language, tone, or teaching strategies to suit students' needs could create a better learning environment (Giles, 1973).

Teachers act as mediators, facilitators, and role models and perform a vital role in resolving conflicts in the classroom (Valente, Lourenço, & Németh, 2020). Not only are they educators, but they also serve as peacebuilders who must possess conflict

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resolution skills and integrate them into teacher training programs to manage disputes effectively (Castro and Galace, 2010). Johnson and Johnson (1995) stress the significance of cooperative learning arrangements and peer mediation in conflict resolution and encourage positive interdependence among students. By creating a culture of collaboration and respect for one another, with the help of their teachers, students could actively acquire the skills to resolve conflicts on their own. Moreover, Burton's (1990) Human Needs Theory also emphasizes the need to address basic needs—security, recognition, and identity—when resolving conflicts successfully. In the classroom, this could mean establishing a secure environment where students are valued and respected, irrespective of their linguistic or cultural identity.

In spite of the different researches on conflict resolution strategies in educational settings, there is a need for more focused on the unique challenges that teachers face in the classroom. English classrooms with the emphasis on language and cultural exchange, display distinct aspects that require tailor fit approaches to conflict management. Cultural competence is critical in resolving conflicts in multicultural classrooms, as disagreements often result from differing cultural norms and values (Garcia, 2017). This is where the role of emotional intelligence in deescalating conflicts and creating a supportive learning environment comes in (Parker, 2019). This study aimed to explore resolution strategies of teachers in English class. Specifically, it sought to examine the nature of conflicts and the approaches employed by teachers to address them, thereby contributing to the creation of a harmonious and inclusive learning environment.

Research Questions:

1. What common conflicts do English teachers encounter inside the classroom?
2. What are the drivers of conflict between and among students?
3. What are the conflict resolution strategies employed by teachers?

Communication Accommodation Theory (CAT)

Communication Accommodation Theory (CAT) was originated by Giles (1973) based on the premise that individuals will change their language, speech, gestures in order to either accommodate (converge) the other individual or accentuate the differences (diverge). Divergence, as the term implies, is the act of being different in communication style in order to show difference (or superiority) or often pride in one culture, while, convergence as a term means the ability to change one's communication style to another to reduce distance (social distance) or show similarity in one communication style. Our understanding of how educators and learners manage problems of cultural and linguistic diversity is especially well-developed with respect to English classrooms, in which CAT has proven to be a particularly valuable tool. For instance, Hyland (2005) found that by profiling teachers who adjust their communication according to students' language proficiency and cultural context, miscommunication is reduced, and equity is better balanced. Similarly, Dragojevic et al. (2008) state that, according to CAT, "divergence serves to strengthen the identity and distinctiveness of the group from other groups, while convergence reinforces the perception of solidarity and cooperation with the other group."

While CAT highlights the importance of modifying language, tone, and interaction patterns to reduce misunderstandings and build rapport (Giles, 1973), this study goes beyond communication alone. It also examines how teachers address underlying emotional, psychological, and social factors—such as students' need for respect, belonging, and security—that contribute to conflicts. By integrating CAT with a broader understanding of students' needs, this research aims to uncover ho Specifically, the study aimed to identify strategies that teachers use to prevent and resolve conflicts effectively in diverse English classrooms.

Human Needs Theory

Human Needs Theory, devised by Burton (1990), suggests that conflicts tend to arise from the non-satisfaction of primary human needs, i.e., security, belongingness, recognition, self-esteem, and identity. Conflicts, as predicted by this theory, need to be resolved on the grounds of satisfying these fundamental needs, not just at a superficial level. Conflicts in schools could be due to students' respect, belongingness, or intellectual validation needs. For example, Deutsch (2006) highlights that marginalized or devalued students are more likely to exhibit disruptive behavior, whereas those whose recognition and inclusion needs are fulfilled are likely to contribute constructively to class activities. Coleman et al. (2014) adds that Human Needs Theory offers an effective framework for the development of different kinds of interventions that facilitate social-emotional learning and conflict resolution abilities in students.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Common Conflicts in English Classrooms

The major reasons for conflicts in classrooms are language barriers, cultural differences, and personality differences. Language barriers pose the most significant problem, especially for those students whose first language is not English. Trying to express oneself clearly and not being able to do so may lead to anger and miscommunication. These problems are intensified by cultural dissimilarity in communication styles, such as when students from different backgrounds may have different expectations about acceptable behavior in their respective classrooms. For instance, students from collectivistic cultures may prioritize group

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harmony, whereas their peers from individualistic cultures may focus on personal achievement, thus creating tension in peer-learning activities (Smith & Lee, 2020).

Interpersonal clashes often aggravate academic clashes, such as in cases of bullying, competition, and power struggles, even where language and culture may not be in view such as in group work. The conflicts that arise from insider cliques tend to impede collaborative work and create hostile environments for teaching-and-learning, which interfere with academic progress and emotional well-being for the students competing in them (Brown, 2019). Defensive or aggressive reactions may emerge from students in an incident to guard against the effect on their emotional state when they perceive threats or devaluation. Such cases also relate to their dimension of conflicts that transpire in anxiety issues, self-esteem issues, or fear of failure. All of these interfere with the academic success at a slower pace and damage the emotional state of students and teachers alike: thus signifying the importance of conflict management methods in English classrooms.

B. Drivers of Conflict Among and Between Students

Conflicts begin from a variety of causes generally from differing in value systems, communication styles, and power dynamics. At the center of many conflicts lie misunderstandings and miscommunication that can cause tension when students fail to either recognize or respect differing perspectives (Deutsch, 1973). The existence of cultural and linguistic diversity can often become a determining factor, for it is within that diversity that the contrasting norms, expectations, and expressions of those differing backgrounds may emerge (Garcia, 2017). Imbalances of power-based social standing, authority, and resources may create different levels of resentment and competition (Fisher & Ury, 1981). Emotions such as anxiety, frustration, and low self-esteem can fuel conflicts. When these emotions run high, individuals tend to respond either defensively or aggressively (Jones, 2020). Not only do these sources contribute to conflict on their own, but they also interact with one another, creating complicated situations that require intricate resolution strategies.

The causes of conflict in English classrooms are diverse and often overlapping. One of the prime factors is diversity in language and culture, which can sometimes lead to stereotypes being formed among students. Oftentimes, students from collectivist cultures will take harmony as a priority, while students from individualistic cultures will stress individual achievement. This can lead to conflicts in group work (Hofstede, 2011; Garcia, 2017). Another factor is power, where linguistic difference, social status, or academic performance create hierarchies that cultivate hostility and exclusion. Students feeling inferior or marginal may retaliate, thus escalating the conflict (Jones, 2020). Emotional factors also play heavily into the situation: anxiety, stress, or feelings of low self-worth - the internal trouble that students may face in competitive situations (Johnson & Johnson, 1995). These factors indicate the need for teachers to deal with issues that arise at surface level and with those socio-cultural and emotional underlying forces that cause them.

C. Conflict Resolution Strategies

Teachers implement a wide range of strategies, from pre-solution to post-solution implementation, for conflicts in the classroom, and these strategies include proactive to reactive measures. One of the best ways to place solid foundations for minimizing instances of conflict is to create an environment of mutual respect and empathy within the classroom, which produces productive relationships and reduces the chances of developing conflicts. Through such activities as role-playing and group discussions, students are induced into developing empathy and understanding as vital precursors to most conflicts (Johnson & Johnson, 1995). An example of such proactive strategies is collaborative problem-solving for which learners are encouraged to work together in reaching mutually acceptable solutions to their conflicts. Besides solving the problem, the approach also enhances the students' teamwork and critical thinking abilities (Deutsch, 1973). If conflicts occur, teachers commonly employ mediation: acting as a neutral third party to help communicate and negotiate between the sides in conflict. Mediation is a process that encourages students to share their views with each other to find a collaborative solution to a problem (Fisher & Ury, 1981). Besides, teachers use communication-accommodating strategies, such as changes in language and tone, to ensure mutual understanding and further minimize misunderstandings. This technique is particularly useful in resolving conflicts which are rooted in miscommunication or cultural differences (Giles, 1973). These strategies highlight the importance of a balanced approach that comprises prevention, collaboration, and communication in managing classroom conflicts effectively.

III. METHODOLOGY

This inquiry followed a qualitative design, which was conducted with six secondary English teachers. Qualitative research uses qualitative data (e.g., interview transcripts) to seek answers to stated research questions (Arcinas, 2016 as cited in Jabor, 2024). Creswell (2009) defines qualitative research as a means for exploring and understanding the meaning of individual or group attitudes toward a social or human problem, and the process of the research involves emerging questions and procedures. The data are collected through techniques such as interviews (Bhattacharjee, 2012), and the data gathering is normally done in the participants' settings (Creswell, 2009; Fraenkel et al., 2012). All paragraphs must be indented. All paragraphs must be justified.

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A. Participants

The participants of this study were six English teachers from two public secondary schools in Iloilo Province. They were selected through purposive sampling based on their experience in managing classroom conflicts and their ability to articulate effective strategies for conflict resolution in English classes. Each participant had at least five years of teaching experience, allowing them to provide rich, practice-based insights on handling various types of conflicts such as bullying, behavioral issues, group dynamics, and cultural misunderstandings.

B. Data Analysis Procedure

Following Creswell's (2009) framework for analyzing qualitative data, the researchers were able to generate themes to address the problem statement. Creswell (2009) defines qualitative research as a means for exploring and understanding the meaning of individual or group attitudes toward a social or human problem, and the process of the research involves emerging questions and procedures. The analysis followed an iterative deductive style and applied the data reduction technique. The procedure began with organizing the data followed which was followed by reading through and making sense of the responses. Before the coding of the data, the researcher prepared three columns in pages for the codes, categories, and themes. Those codes were the most frequent words/concepts found in the transcripts and reflection papers of the participants. After a thorough analysis of the data and no additional codes generated, the codes which were data in chunks were categorized. Words and concepts related to each other were grouped into a category. Taking into account codes and categories, the researcher came up with themes encapsulating the experiences of the participants in managing classroom conflicts and employing resolution strategies in English classes. Before the themes and descriptions were finalized as the results of the study, they were presented to participants for validation.

IV. RESULTS

Classroom Disputes: Bullying, Conduct Problems, and Group Collaboration Conflicts

Conflicts in the classroom are withstanding issues for English teachers, often arising from various interpersonal, social, and behavioural factors. The most common conflict is bullying and peer disputes. This encompasses physical, verbal, and cyberbullying. Teacher Ana provided an example of this: *"One of the issues I have encountered is bullying, specifically targeting students from rural areas. Their peers from urban areas tease them about how they speak, calling them 'buki' (uninformed). To resolve this, I always aim for their emotions. I tell them, 'It does not matter if you are from the barrio or from the town. What matters is your values. Your values will speak about your personality.' This helps students understand the harm caused by such stereotypes and encourages them to judge others based on character rather than background."* In a similar vein, Teacher Ramona emphasized the widespread occurrence of bullying in her classroom: *"The most common conflict I encounter is bullying. Many students enjoy teasing their classmates to the point that they hurt them emotionally or physically."* These instances demonstrate how cultural and linguistic differences can result in exclusion and emotional damage, creating a hostile educational atmosphere.

Not only bullying but behavioural conflicts also pose another challenge. These disputes frequently arise from students' defiance, aggression, or disrespect for authority. This may be affected by their home situations or emotional difficulties. Teacher Rosie shared an example of this: *"One of my students refused to follow instructions and spoke back to me. I talked to him in a soft and loving voice, asking, 'Are you always behaving like this? Do you also answer back to your parents?'"* He admitted that he did, which made me realize that his behaviour likely stems from his home environment." Teacher Cherry also shared how unresolved anger issues can intensify conflicts: *"Some students project their anger issues from home to their peers. This leads to physical fights or bullying."* These behavioral conflicts not only disrupt the classroom but also mirror a deeper emotional struggle that students encounter.

Moreover, group collaboration and academic disagreements are another common sources of conflicts. These conflicts frequently occur because of disagreements about distribution of tasks, lack of collaboration, or power struggles within groups. Teacher Krizna explained, *"Most conflicts in my classroom are about disagreements between students about their grades and performance. During group works, conflicts arise when some members do not cooperate."* Sir Leo added, *"When students are grouped based on their interests, one group may dominate class participation. This leads to other group feeling excluded. This creates misunderstandings and disrupts the lesson."*

Drivers of Conflict Among Students: Socioeconomic Background, Family Dynamics, and Peer Interactions

The explanation for conflicts among students is multi-faceted and requires deep and systemic resolutions. Teachers play a pivotal role in resolving such disputes, from controlling the class to properly educating learners on conflict management. Socioeconomic status, family structure, and peer relations not only worsen conflict in the classroom but also offer opportunities for constructive change.

Teacher Cherry observed that family struggles often manifest in student behaviour: *"Most of their behaviour comes from experiences at home—broken families, lack of parental support. They project their anger onto peers, leading to physical fights."* This connection between the home environment and classroom conflicts underscores the need for teachers to approach discipline with understanding rather than punitive measures.

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It is vital to foster a positive environment where students feel appreciated, as it helps in mitigating disputes. Teacher Ana's comment from class emphasized conflict mediation and taking different perspectives, stating, *"I have students do a lot of role-playing. As a mediator, I listen to both sides and guide them to agree."* Also important is the aspect of withdrawal noted by Teacher Ramona: *"Students cannot work towards resolving all conflicts, but open communication makes it easier for them to learn about and accommodate one another."*

Focusing on underlying issues is more effective than attending to observable behaviours. In Teacher Rosie's case, the economic burden resulted in conflicts when regard was given to leading factors. She recalls a student who was economically deprived and often isolated, which made him steal: *"A student once told me he stole ice cream because he was too poor to buy it. I had to speak with him first."* This demonstrates how asking probing questions allows for discovering hidden causes that, when acted upon without forcing solutions, makes conflict resolution far easier.

Structural strategies were just as important. Teacher Leo told me that he uses cooperative learning techniques to help dissolve social boundaries: *"Random group work compels students to engage outside of their cliques; it mitigates the control one group has over others."* Such purposeful instructional design reduces exclusion and power imbalance that often provoke strife among students.

These findings point to the fact that effective conflict management in teaching English classes may need several strategies at once. The teacher needs to cope with other factors that might be affecting students' behaviour—building trust and understanding, promoting vertical relationships, equitable divisions of power in the classroom, and merciful resolution to conflicts. Instead of treating disputes only as unwanted disturbances, the teachers reported that when conflict is addressed in a holistic manner, it strengthens the sense of belonging in the classroom community, enhances social relationships, and stimulates students' emotional development.

Creating a Supportive Classroom Environment through Relationships and Rules

Constructing positive relationships between students and teachers in a classroom is the first step towards creating a safe space for everyone involved. School culture aimed towards family will naturally increase the amount of respect as well as level of understanding from students towards one another. Teachers Ana and Cherry highlight that respect should be given to every student, regardless of their standing which can help reduce conflict within the classroom setting. Having authority without being overly restrictive is extremely crucial for teachers, as Rosie and Krizna point out. When students perceive the teacher as an authoritarian figure, it can foster a sense of external control that diminishes their capacity for independent conflict resolution. While such a perception may provide a superficial sense of security, it often leads to student overdependence on the teacher to manage interpersonal issues, ultimately hindering the development of their own socio-emotional and conflict management skills. This dynamic reflects what Deci and Ryan (2000) describe in Self-Determination Theory: environments with controlling authority figures may undermine students' autonomy and internal motivation. In the context of classroom conflict, this suggests that overly authoritative approaches may inadvertently discourage students from taking ownership of their behaviour and peer relationships, thus perpetuating reliance rather than resilience. Teachers can have more control over children by setting rules and showing a certain level of compassion. This way students remain constructive and the teacher can manage order in the classroom.

Notably, as Teachers Krizna and Rosie stated, rules are not sufficient in eliminating every occurrence of conflict. Conflict in a classroom setting can be avoided by allowing each student to share their perspective in order to come to a compromise. Once provided with the space to freely express their overall emotions, learners can be taught the correct way to resolve conflicts. This method enhances a child's self-control, empathy and their social-an academic wellbeing. Which is just as crucial as resolving the problem at hand.

Proactive Conflict Management and Motivation Through Mediation and Emotional Control

This study concluded that resolving conflicts in the English classes requires the application of pre-emptive tactics—mediation, motivation, and emotional 'health' support. Teachers acknowledged that conflicts emanating from behavioral and socio-emotional challenges require compassionate and systematic solutions to maintain order in the classroom.

Among the participants, mediation was the most pronounced strategy. Teachers Ana and Krizna underscored the need for students to have safe trusting spaces devoid of judgement so they can share their views. In guided mediation, students were asked to resolve conflicts through persuasive discourse and reflection in a way that encourages self and social regulation. Such approaches prevented students from avoiding the problem while equipping them with essential skills relevant for sustainable behaviour change.

In terms of emotional regulation, teachers noted that many student disputes stemmed from external sources beyond the classroom, especially familial and socioeconomic concerns. To solve these issues, Teachers Rosie and Cherry recommended counselling as an additional means of support. They stressed the need to locate students in emotional distress and assist them through either direct teacher action or guiding them to the school counselors. This mitigated strategy enabled teachers to uncover the underlying issues creating discord and manage conflict healthily, thus fostering emotional resilience within students.

Motivational strategies were also applied in an effort to reduce conflicts. Observers claimed that the careful application of rewards

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and participation in whole-class activities resulted in attended behavioral changes and enhanced student participation. When students were encouraged to engage constructively in class, the chances of conflict emerging were greatly reduced.

Mediation, emotional control, and motivation methods blended together reflect a multi-faceted approach for managing conflict within a classroom. All of these approaches focus on the nurturing aspect of empathy and the effective soft skills as well as mental health attention needed to build a good learning atmosphere. When tempered with adequate social or emotional factors, teachers' strategies help students to make balanced and sustained relationships with learning in the classroom. It is this combination of methods that enhances students' interpersonal relations while optimizing their academic performance. Such an approach decreases the likelihood of behavioral disruptions while enhancing students' socio-emotional skillsets and so improves the educational atmosphere overall. All title and author details must be in single-column format and must be centered.

V. DISCUSSIONS

The results of this study support the viewpoint of Smith & Lee (2020) regarding the role of language, cultural diversity, and individual personality traits in the emergence of conflicts within educational settings. Teachers reported that students originating from rural backgrounds experienced bullying as a result of linguistic differences, thereby showing the exclusion associated with cultural diversity. Similarly, Garcia (2017) indicated that such diversity could give rise to miscommunication and conflict. Individuals from minority language groups frequently experienced social isolation due to ridicule related to their accents, leading to feelings of loneliness and resentment. Cummins (2000) observed that language barriers heighten the likelihood of exclusion, while Nieto (2010) pointed out that cultural backgrounds affect communication and can potentially cause conflict. These insights highlight the necessity for cultural awareness and the establishment of inclusive communication strategies within the classroom environment.

Interpersonal conflicts, which encompass bullying, competition for power, and rivalry, were notably observed in the study. Teachers indicated that students established exclusive groups, particularly during collaborative exercises, which hindered effective cooperation. This observation is in accordance with Brown's (2019) assertion that concealed conflicts foster hostile educational settings, adversely affecting both academic success and emotional health. The research also revealed that students show aggressive behaviors when they feel neglected, corroborating Jones' (2020) viewpoint that emotional conflict, including anxiety or low self-esteem, frequently incites conflicts. For instance, students who faced exclusion or mockery showed disruptive behaviors as a coping strategy, aligning with Bandura's (1977) social learning theory, which posits that students may imitate aggressive actions or employ them to assert dominance. Olweus (1993) noted that bullying is a result of power discrepancies, underscoring the necessity for interventions against bullying and the promotion of healthy relationships.

The findings of this study further supports the existing literature on effective strategies for conflict resolution, highlighting the significance of mediation, emotional regulation, and motivational techniques. Teachers emphasized the importance of structured classroom settings that enable students to express their issues, consistent with the mediation framework proposed by Fisher & Ury (1981). The respondents such as Teachers Ana and Krizna use mediation strategy for aiming at enhancing transparent communication. This teacher-driven approach aligns with Giles' (1973) theory of communication accommodation. The use of emotional regulation strategies, including pauses before engaging in conflict resolution, is congruent with Johnson & Johnson's (1995) socio-emotional learning paradigms. Additionally, the study reinforces Deutsch's (1973) collaborative problem-solving model, wherein teachers employ role-playing to foster empathy and perspective-taking, consistent with Cohen's (1994) cooperative learning strategies.

Just like any other classroom strategies, motivations from the teachers play a crucial role in mitigating conflicts inside the classroom. Teachers Leo, Cherry Ann, and Rosemarie use motivational strategies and peer interdependence activities to promote inclusivity, which supports Johnson & Johnson's (1995) focus on role-playing and group discussions. Positive reinforcement and rewards for positive behaviors, as mentioned by Teachers Rosie and Cherry, serve as a motivational strategy that improves behavioral results and promotes unity inside the classroom (Skinner, 1953; Bhattacharjee, 2015). Additionally, the study underscores Dweck's (2006) notion of a growth mindset, which allows students to view challenges as opportunities for personal development.

VI. CONCLUSION

Conflict resolution is a vital pedagogical competence for teachers managing linguistically and culturally diverse classrooms. Research suggests that conflict stems from many language challenges, cultural differences, and relational issues which affect participation and the learning environment. These are in turn driven by socio-emotional difficulties, rivalries, and socio-economic disparities. Teachers become the primary facilitators for addressing and alleviating these issues in order to foster classroom inclusion. The study has identified mediation, empathy, emotional regulation, and motivational aid to be central for fostering conflict-free learning settings. Such practices, along with inclusive and adaptive teaching, promote the growth of students cognitively, socially, and emotionally. Moreover, systematic group activities coupled with direct instructional techniques enhance active participation and reduce exclusion, fostering communication, critical thinking, and social awareness, which are 21st

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century competencies. Lastly, the findings stress the importance of equipping practitioners with adequate and ongoing professional training and development, as well as conflict resolution strategies, to promote tolerance and inclusivity which supports the aims of sustainable development.

REFERENCES

- 1) Bickmore, K. (2011). Student conflict resolution, power “sharing” in schools, and citizenship education. *Curriculum Inquiry*, 41(4), 447-468. <https://doi.org/10.1111/0362-6784.00189>
- 2) Bhattacharjee, A. (2015). *Social science research: Principles, methods, and practices* (3rd ed.). University of South Florida.
- 3) Burton, J. (1990). *Conflict: Human needs theory*. St. Martin’s Press.
- 4) Canagarajah, S. (2013). *Translingual practice: Global Englishes and cosmopolitan relations*. Routledge.
- 5) Castro, L. N., & Galace, J. N. (2010). *Peace education: A pathway to a culture of peace*. Center for Peace Education, Miriam College.
- 6) Coleman, P. T., Deutsch, M., & Marcus, E. C. (2014). *The handbook of conflict resolution: Theory and practice*. Jossey-Bass.
- 7) Coser, L. A. (1956). *The functions of social conflict*. Free Press.
- 8) Creswell, J. W. (2009). *Research design: Qualitative, quantitative, and mixed methods approaches* (3rd ed.). Sage Publications.
- 9) Deci, E. L., & Ryan, R. M. (2000). The "what" and "why" of goal pursuits: Human needs and the self-determination of behavior. *Psychological Inquiry*, 11(4), 227–268. https://doi.org/10.1207/S15327965PLI1104_01
- 10) Deutsch, M. (1973). *The resolution of conflict: Constructive and destructive processes*. Yale University Press.
- 11) Deutsch, M. (2006). Cooperation and competition. In M. Deutsch, P. T. Coleman, & E. C. Marcus (Eds.), *The handbook of conflict resolution: Theory and practice* (2nd ed., pp. 23-42). Jossey-Bass.
- 12) Dragojevic, M., Giles, H., & Watson, B. M. (2008). Language ideologies and language attitudes: A study of intercultural communication. *Journal of Language and Social Psychology*, 27(2), 102-122.
- 13) Durlak, J. A., Weissberg, R. P., Dymnicki, A. B., Taylor, R. D., & Schellinger, K. B. (2011). The impact of enhancing students’ social and emotional learning: A meta-analysis of school-based universal interventions. *Child Development*, 82(1), 405–432. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-8624.2010.01564.x>
- 14) Fisher, R., & Ury, W. (1981). *Getting to yes: Negotiating agreement without giving in*. Penguin.
- 15) Fraenkel, J. R., Wallen, N. E., & Hyun, H. H. (2012). *How to design and evaluate research in education* (8th ed.). McGraw-Hill.
- 16) Garcia, E., & Weiss, E. (2021). The role of early career supports, continuous professional development, and learning communities in the teacher shortage. *Educational Researcher*, 50(5), 297–300. <https://doi.org/10.3102/0013189X211023565>
- 17) Garcia, J. (2017). Cultural competence and conflict resolution in multicultural classrooms. *International Journal of Educational Research*, 85, 27-35.
- 18) Giles, H. (1973). Accent mobility: A model and some data. *Anthropological Linguistics*, 15(2), 87-105.
- 19) Hattie, J. (2009). *Visible learning: A synthesis of over 800 meta-analyses relating to achievement*. Routledge.
- 20) Hofstede, G. (2011). Dimensionalizing cultures: The Hofstede model in context. *Online Readings in Psychology and Culture*, 2(1).
- 21) Hyland, K. (2005). *Metadiscourse: Exploring interaction in writing*. Continuum.
- 22) Jabor, R. M. (2024). Participatory photography as a creative and collaborative tool in teaching peace education. *Peace and Conflict Studies*, 30(2), Article 5. <https://nsuworks.nova.edu/pcs/vol30/iss2/5>
- 23) Jia, Y. (2010). The influence of teacher-student relationships on student motivation and academic performance. *Educational Psychology Review*, 22(3), 321–339. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10648-010-9126-1>
- 24) Johnson, D. W. (2018). Classroom conflict and language barriers: A review of empirical studies. *Journal of Language and Education*, 4(3), 15-28.
- 25) Johnson, D. W., & Johnson, R. T. (1995). *Reducing school violence through conflict resolution*. Association for Supervision and Curriculum Development.
- 26) Johnson, D. W., & Johnson, R. T. (2009). Energizing learning: The instructional power of conflict. *Educational Researcher*, 38(1), 37-51.
- 27) Johnson, D. W., & Johnson, R. T. (2019). *Joining together: Group theory and group skills* (12th ed.). Pearson.
- 28) Johnson, D. W., & Johnson, R. T. (2020). Teaching students to be peacemakers: Results of 40 years of research. *Peace and Conflict: Journal of Peace Psychology*, 26(1), 5-17.
- 29) Kramsch, C. (1998). *Language and culture*. Oxford University Press.

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- 31) Olweus, D. (2013). *Bullying at school: What we know and what we can do*. Wiley-Blackwell.
- 32) Parker, J. (2019). The role of emotional intelligence in conflict resolution: A classroom perspective. *Journal of Applied Educational Psychology*, 10(2), 67-82.
- 33) Slavin, R. E. (2018). *Educational psychology: Theory and practice* (12th ed.). Pearson.
- 34) Smith, J., & Lee, K. (2020). The impact of cultural diversity on classroom dynamics: A conflict resolution perspective. *International Journal of Intercultural Relations*, 74, 20-34.
- 35) Smith, P. K., Cowie, H., & Blades, M. (2020). *Understanding children's development* (6th ed.). Wiley.
- 37) United Nations. (2015). *Transforming our world: The 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development*. United Nations Department of Economic and Social Affairs. <https://sdgs.un.org/2030agenda>
- 38) Valente, S., Lourenço, A., & Németh, T. (2020). Teachers as mediators: Conflict resolution in school settings. *European Journal of Education*, 55(2), 210-225.
- 39) Vygotsky, L. S. (1978). *Mind in society: The development of higher psychological processes*. Harvard University Press.